
FACTOR DETERMINANTS OF FAMILY-OWNED BUSINESS FAILURES: A STUDY OF EKENEDIRICHUKWU TRANSPORT COMPANY IN ENUGU, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study examined factor determinants of family-owned business failures: A study of Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to investigate the effect of succession planning on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria and ascertain the effect of family conflict on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted. The total population was 35 employees while sample size was 35 using purposive sampling techniques. Structured questionnaire was used as instrument of data collection. The study revealed that succession planning had a significant positive effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria and family conflict had a significant positive influence on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria. The study concluded that factor determinants of family-owned business failures had significant positive effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria. The study recommended that managers of Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company should consider succession planning and family conflict resolution as powerful tools to checkmate family business failure.

Keywords: Family-Owned Business, Succession Planning, Family Conflict, Business Failure, Transport Company

INTRODUCTION

Family business which is a unique, complex and dynamic system often consists of a blend of two very different poles. At one of the poles is a performance-based world of business and at the other end there is the emotion-based domain of the family which results into potential conflict and confusion (Ibrahim & Ellis, 2021). A family business is any operations in which majority of the management rest within a family and in most cases two or more family members are often involved in the day-to-day affairs of such ventures. It is a business management combination of the family and the business. The families that are involved in the business are part of a task system (the business) and part of a family system as well. Mita (2019), a family business is a venture that is mainly owned by the members of a single family. Simply put, it is a business in which members of a

family have major control and ownership as well as key commitments toward the overall wellbeing of the business (Agbaeze, *et al*, 2019).

FOB's have their place in history as they have existed for a very long time hence, they are regarded as the oldest form of business. De Alwis (2020) posits that FOB's represent the oldest and most prevalent type of business organizations worldwide. However, despite their place as the oldest and making major contributions to the economy, their survival rate appears to be appalling as only a handful of them survive more than one generation. Ogundele (2022) opines that despite the importance of FOBs to the national economy, their survival rate beyond the founder's generation is extremely low especially in Nigeria.

Generally, family businesses regardless of their size often face significant challenges that emanate from the issues such as continuity, longevity, and successes. Many of these businesses failed to sustain their firms beyond the first generation. In Nigeria, the story of the growth of family-controlled enterprises is generally considered dramatic because of the amount of pitfalls that are faced by these firms before they go on to be successful. While some of these family businesses have become successful, others have failed while some are simply basking in the shadow of their former selves. The growth of family businesses is a critical element that determines the growth of most less-developed economies and they hold particular implication for Nigeria as well. Family businesses do not only contribute significantly to improved living standards but they also create a significant level of capital and achieve high levels of production and increased capacity (Agbaeze, *et al*, 2019).

Ifekwen, *et al*. (2021) developing economies like African and Asian countries have come to realize the value and significant role family-controlled enterprises play in their economic development and growth. In most of the developing countries, much of the entrepreneurship activities and wealth lies with family-controlled enterprises thereby making family businesses to become the fastest growing sector of their economy. Family businesses come in different ranges of firms in different sectors and sizes for any economy. They come in form of sole proprietors to large international enterprises. International Finance Corporation (2022), states that family-owned enterprises range from small and medium-sized companies to large conglomerates operating in many countries and economies. It is important to note that family business and small business are not necessarily analogous. Though there are many large organizations that are seen as family-owned enterprises, but the majority of family businesses are considered small businesses with less than 20 employees (U.S. Small Business Administration, 1997).

Stating this differently, Burns (2022) posits that it is only about 30% of family-owned businesses that will survive the transition from the first generation down to the second generation and only 12% will remain after companies' transition to the third generation and these family-owned businesses are looking at only a 3% survival rate when transitioning to the fourth generation and beyond. It is estimated that less than one-third of family firms survived into the second generation and only 13 percent survived through the third generation (Ogundele, 2022). In Nigeria, this trend of firm closure is even more prevalent as Ogundele (2022) posits. He states that this situation is worse in Nigeria as many FOB's, however promising and vibrant have closed down at the death of their founder.

A host of factors has been attributed to the death of FOB's all over the world. Some of the factors include lack of planning, not keeping abreast with the economic situations, paucity of funds, taxation, reckless spending. However, more importantly is the absence or lack of succession planning in these businesses. Ogundele (2022),

posits that many FOB's close down due to lack of adequate planning for succession. Onuoha (2018) explicates that a popular real estate business in Aba fizzled out immediately after the death of the founder in 2005; no successor owner or manager. The large compound of a renowned transporter has remained desolate in Port Harcourt since the owner-manager died in 2009; again, no successor manager or owner (Burns, 2022).

Statement of Problem

Ayobami, Odey, Olanireti and Babarinde (2018) listed the following as factors inhibiting family businesses in Nigeria, they are: lack of infrastructural facilities, poor financial management, funding, competition. Internal and external problems, according to Adedeji (1981), obstruct family business. Family enterprises, on the other hand, have a high failure rate, particularly in Nigeria. According to statistics, 95% of family-owned businesses in Nigeria do not make it to the third generation. Governments, policymakers, family company owners, and future entrepreneurs should all be concerned about this. Apart from the well-known challenges that contribute to business failures in Nigeria, such as deteriorating infrastructure, inconsistent government policies, family conflict and double taxation, among others, the lack of a succession plan is a serious issue that threatens the survival and continuity of these family businesses (Olubiyi, 2021). Buttressing this point, Onuoha (2018) state that the lack of succession planning in Nigeria is a serious problem militating against the survival of family-owned businesses as 94.2% of entrepreneurs do not have a succession plan.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to investigate factor determinants of family-owned business failures: A study of Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria. Specifically, were to;

- i. Investigate the effect of succession planning on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the effect of family conflict on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Family-Owned Business

Family-Owned Business (FOB) just like the name implies is a business that is owned by a family. There is however, no universality in its definition despite its huge impact on the economy of nations and the number of research interest in the field. Buttressing this point, Harms (2014), explicates that in spite of long-standing scientific research on FOB issues and the considerable economic relevance of this group of companies, no jointly accepted definition exists within the research field.

Suh, Park and Park (2018) point out that there are definition difficulties in FOB definition but it could be defined using some of the following criteria: voting control, percentage of ownership, power over strategic direction, involvement of multiple generations, and active management by family members. Thus, Cabrera-Suarez (2015), opines that FOB can be defined as a business in which the family has influence or control over both the ownership and management operations.

To Allouche and Amann (2018) a FOB is a business in which one or several families significantly influence its development through ownership of its capital, placing the emphasis on family ties with regard to the process of selecting company directors, whether they are family members or workers recruited externally, and expressing a

desire to transmit the business to the next generation while understanding the importance of the business for the interests and objectives of the family.

Factor Determinants of Family-Owned Business

Succession Planning

Succession planning under the study is one of the independent variables. Therefore, succession planning is a strategy for handing over leadership responsibilities and, in certain cases, corporate ownership to an individual or group of workers (Kenton & Perez, 2020). Succession planning guarantees that a company's operations continue to function efficiently when its most key personnel retire or leave. Employees are cross-trained to build skills, corporate knowledge, and a holistic view of the organization as part of succession planning (Kenton & Perez, 2020). Succession planning is a method and approach for determining who will take over leadership responsibilities in the future. It's utilized to find and train new leaders who can step into leadership responsibilities when they become available.

Family Conflict

Nevertheless, family conflict which is a form of intra-group conflict is the focus of this study and one of the independent variables. Family conflict according to Malek (2018) is any conflict that occurs within a family; between husbands and wives, parents and children, between siblings, or with extended families (grandparents, aunts, uncles, etc.). Family conflict is different from other types of conflict for several reasons. First, family members are already highly emotionally attached. These emotions can quickly intensify conflict. Secondly, family members are involved in long-term relationships and often are required to interact with one another daily. Finally, families are often insular, obeying their own rules and resisting outside interference.

Performance

Firm performance is connected to effective use of performance measures in the family firm. Firms because of the accelerating growth of internet, business globalization, manufacturing integration, supply chain management, and customer relation management have become the most popular management activities. Customer orientation, learning orientation, entrepreneurial orientation, and innovation orientation are four of the most essential characteristics that might improve the efficiency and effectiveness of these activities. Several studies have been conducted in this subject to analyze business performance in a variety of ways using a variety of strategic techniques (Berthon, Hulbert & Pitt, 2004). In family-owned enterprises, each strategic direction has different effects on growth and profitability. In various studies, positive relationships were found between the active return rate, growth in sales, new product success, increasing market share, and profitability performance indicators.

Conceptual Framework

Conceptual framework for this study is presented in figure 2.1 below. The framework was designed by the researcher based on theoretical underpinnings findings from empirical studies and models related to the study.

**Factor Determinants
(Independent Variables)**

**Ekenedilichukwu Transport
(Dependent Variable)**

Figure 2.1: Model of Factor Determinants of Family-Owned Business Failures and Ekenedilichukwu

Source: Adapted from Emerole, G. A. (2015), Analysis of factors affecting performance of family-owned businesses in Abia State, Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* 17(I) 34-37.

Theoretical Framework

Resource-based View Theory

The study was anchored on resource-based view theory. The resource-based view originally proposed by Birger Wernerfelt (1984) and later developed and refined by Jay B. Barney (1991) and other scholars, the resource-based view of the firm has found considerable support in the business literature. The Resource based view focuses on analysis of the nature, characteristics and potential of a firm's resource base. It has been stated that the idiosyncratic resources and capabilities that are developed when the family system and the business system interact and coexist in harmony are largely responsible for the uniqueness of family businesses (Nordqvist & Melin, 2010). While the theories provide useful insights into family business characteristics, the systems and RBV is the framework that is widely used. RBV, as a conceptual framework has been instrumental in developing a theory for family business (Chrisma, 2007). However, it is relevant to this study because in every business whether family or not, they need resources to survive. So, resource is essential tool businesses needs to adopt in order to make more advancement goals.

Empirical Review

Succession Planning and Performance

Ogbechie and Anetor (2015) carried out a study on appraisal of succession planning in family-owned businesses in Lagos State, Nigeria. The population of the study includes all family-owned enterprises in Lagos state, Nigeria. A purposive sampling technique was employed by the study to select 80 participants (owners/founders of family businesses) from the population. Data was elicited from questionnaire and analyses of the responses were done using descriptive statistics and factor analysis through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). From the findings, it indicated that the lack of a succession plan is not the significant factor responsible for the problem of succession despite the fact that most family enterprises lack succession plan.

Vongani and Clever (2016) investigated the effect of succession planning on business survival: a case study of Kwalit a business consultant in Johannesburg (South Africa). The findings demonstrate that, while KBC did not have succession planning uses in place, the founding directors did implement some kind of succession planning strategy. According to the findings, succession planning is an important activity that should be integrated into a company's strategy creation and planning process.

A research on succession planning and organizational survival was done by Osayande and Okolie (2016) using data from the National Business and Technical Examination Board in Benin City, Nigeria. The study's goal was

to look at the impact of succession planning on organizational survival: Evidence from the Benin City-based National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). The study's findings reveal that predictors have a considerable positive influence on response variables.

In Anambra, South East Nigeria, Onyeukwu and Jekelle (2019) researched leadership succession and sustainability of small family-owned enterprises. The study used a survey research approach and was conducted in the commercial and industrial centres of Onitsha and Nnewi in Anambra State. The sample of 298 registered small company owners was chosen using a basic random sampling procedure. For data collection, a five-point Likert structured 6-item questionnaire was used. In addition, the Paired Sample t-test was used to check for statistical evidence that the mean difference between the paired observations in the hypothesis is substantially different from zero.

Family Conflict and Performance

Kemjika and Obikoya (2017) examined relationship between family conflict, values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Rivers State Nigeria. The study investigated the relationship between family conflict, values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Rivers State. The study adopted correlational design targeted at establishing the relationship between family conflicts, values and school adjustment. The results of the study showed that there is a positive relationship between family conflict, values and school adjustment which are all statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Mokhtar, Ruslan and Abdullah (2021) investigated the relationship between work and family conflict on life satisfaction and quality of life among employees in the health sector in Nigeria. Therefore, this study was conducted to examine the relationship between life satisfaction and quality of life to work and family conflict where a total of 100 respondents with families were selected to participate in this study. The results of the study found that there was a correlation between work family conflict and life satisfaction but not with quality of life. Further discussions on the findings are reported in the article.

Family-Owned Business and Performance

Emerole (2015) analyzed the factors affecting family-owned businesses in Abia state, Nigeria. The Pearson's correlation revealed that there is an existence of a strong positive relationship between annual income of family business operators and the profitability of the family-owned venture at the 1% (highest) level of significance.

Fatunmbi (2017) studied executive competency and sustainability of family-owned business in Lagos and Ogun States of Nigeria. A descriptive research design was used to study 1,806 family-owned businesses registered in Lagos and Ogun states (NAMSE, 2012). A stratified sampling method was used to select 327 enterprises from the two states. Questionnaire was the main instrument for data collection. Data were analysed using the Pearson's Correlation statistical technique with the aid of SPSS software. The study revealed that executive competency significantly affects sustainability of family-owned business.

kam, Sena & Ndamsa (2017) carried out a study in the Northwest and Southwest Regions of Cameroon to identify those factors that influence the sustainability of family-owned businesses so as to propose measures to both the State and Family Business owners that can be put in place to remedy the situation. A survey-based approach was used through purposive sampling technique. Thirty family businesses were studied using

questionnaire and interviews. Both quantitative and qualitative research methods were used and the data were analysed with the aid of SPSS 17 software programs. Descriptive statistics was used to summarize the sampled opinions of the respondents. The results showed that most of the family business initiators do not always have the notion of sustainability in mind before they die and hence do not prepare for succession.

Agbaeze, *et al* (2019) studied do non-family member managers enhance venture performance of family businesses in Nigeria. This study examines the enhancing effect that non-family members play on the performance of family businesses in Nigeria. Survey design was adopted and Data was collected through structured self-studied questionnaire designed on 5-point Likert scale. Based on the analyzed data, the study found a positive relationship between non-family member managers and venture performance among the selected firms because the former enhances the latter.

Gap in Empirical Review

The available literature indicates a serious lack of empirical studies designed to specifically explain the factors of family-owned business failures and performance. Serious gaps also still remain with respect to the causal ordering of the variables involved in the factors of family-owned business failures. Considering that previous researchers do not agree on the factor determinants of family-owned business failures accordingly the constructs developed scholars which previous authors did not make use of. There is a great need for additional evidence to support the factors of family-owned business failures. The related studies were carried out mainly in developed countries outside Africa. Therefore, this study seeks to fill this gap.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted a survey research design based on the nature of the study.

Survey involves asking questions and obtaining answers from the respondents through the use of questionnaire or oral interview or both.

Sources of Data

Primary data were used for the study and this was sourced from the questionnaire issued to respondents' staff of Ekenedilichukwu Transport.

Population of the Study

Population of the study comprised all the employees of Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company Suited in Enugu South Local Government Area of Enugu State. The total population of the study was 38 employees.

Sample Size Determination/ Sampling Techniques

Since the population of individuals was adjudged finite and too small, the study critical used the entire 38 as sample size determination purposively, therefore, the study employed purposive sampling techniques in order to justly unsound mind of human nature.

Data Collection Instruments

Questionnaire was the instrument used in collecting data from the respondent. It was divided into three major parts. Part A was for bio-data of the respondents, Part B contains data on the major research questions

succession planning and family conflict). Part C contains data on the dependent variable (performance). The questions were constructed on a five-points Likert scale ranging from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1).

Methods of Data Analyses

Data collected for this study was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentage while simple regression test was used to test hypotheses.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

Data Presentation

Table 4.1 Copies of the Questionnaire Distributed and Returned

Respondents	Copies of Questionnaire Distributed	Copies Returned	Percentage Returned	Copies not Returned	Percentage not Returned
Employees	38	35	92%	3	8%
Total	38	35	92%	3	8%

Source: Field Survey, 2025

From table 4.1 above, it shows that 35 copies of the questionnaire were duly completed and returned representing 92 percent, while 3 copies of the questionnaire were not duly completed and returned from the respondents representing 8 percent. Therefore, the total of 35 (92%) copies was brought back and gathered or arranged for the analyzing the data.

Table 4.2: Effect of Succession Planning on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

Options (N =300)	SA (Freq %)	A (Freq %)	UD (Freq %)	D (Freq %)	SD (Freq %)	Mean	Remark
Leadership is one of major issue Ekenedirichukwu transport had.	10 50 (29%)	10 50 (29%)	0 0 (0%)	5 1.25 (14%)	10 50 (29%)	35 151.25 100%	4.3(A)
Knowledge no how from other members of the family affected Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company.	10 50 (29%)	10 50 (29%)	0 0 (0%)	5 1.25 (14%)	10 50 (29%)	35 151.25 100%	4.3(A)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Respondents were asked whether leadership is one of major issue Ekenedirichukwu transport had, 10(53%) of respondents strongly agreed, 10(23%) agreed, 0(0%) undecided, 5(1.25%) disagreed and 10(29%) agreed.

Majority of the respondents strongly agreed that leadership is one of major issue Ekenedirichukwu transport had.

Respondents were questioned whether knowledge no how from other members of the family affected Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company, 10(53%) of respondents strongly agreed, 10(23%) agreed, 0(0%) undecided, 5(1.25%) disagreed and 10(29%) agreed. Majority of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed that knowledge no how from other members of the family affected Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company.

Table 4.3: Effect of Family Conflict on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

Options (N =300)	SA (Freq %)	A (Freq %)	UD (Freq %)	D (Freq %)	SD (Freq %)	Mean	Remark
Family conflict always leads to failure.	10 50 (29%)	10 50 (29%)	0 0 (0%)	5 1.25 (14%)	10 50 (29%)	35 151.25 100%	4.3(A)
Family conflict given based on business merit.	10 50 (29%)	10 50 (29%)	0 0 (0%)	5 1.25 (14%)	10 50 (29%)	35 151.25 100%	4.3(A)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Respondents were asked whether family conflict always leads to failure, 10(53%) of respondents strongly agreed, 10(23%) agreed, 0(0%) undecided, 5(1.25%) disagreed and 10(29%) agreed. Majority of the respondents strongly agreed that family conflict always leads to failure.

Respondents were questioned whether family conflict given based on business merit, 10(53%) of respondents strongly agreed, 10(23%) agreed, 0(0%) undecided, 5(1.25%) disagreed and 10(29%) agreed. Majority of the respondents strongly agreed that family conflict given based on business merit.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Succession planning does not have significant positive effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

H_{a1}: Succession planning have significant positive effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

Table 4.4 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate

1	.250a	.065	.047	.45468
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Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

Predictors: (Constant), Succession planning. Table above revealed that there is a significant positive effect at $R = .250$ between succession planning and performance. An examination of the table shows that the R square = $.063$ which implies that succession planning accounts for only 6.3% of variations having a significant positive effect on performance.

Table 4.5 ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign
1 Regression	2.503	3	.834	4.035	.008b
Residual	37.417	32	.207		
Total	39.921	35			

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

a. Dependent Variable: performance b. Predictors: (Constant), succession planning Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (0.834) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.207), yielding $F=4.035$. The model in this table shows that succession planning statistically and significantly at (Sig =.008) and had a significant positive effect at $F(3,184) = 4.035$. The statistical results is given as; (succession planning $\beta = .019$; $t = .171$; $p > 0.05$). The statistical result implies that succession planning has statistically significant positive influence on Ekenedilichukwu.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Family conflict does not have significant positive effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

H_{a2}: Family conflict have significant positive effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

Table 4.6 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.740a	.548	.541	.33794

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

Predictors: (Constant), Ekenedilichukwu Table above revealed that there is a significant positive effect at $R = .740$ between family conflict and Ekenedilichukwu. An examination of the table shows that the $R^2 = .548$ which implies that family conflict for 54.8% of variations having a significant positive effect on Ekenedilichukwu.

Table 4.7 ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign
1 Regression	25.064	3	.8355	73.155	.008b
Residual	20.671	32	.114		
Total	45.75	35			

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025

a. Dependent Variable: Ekenedilichukwu b. Predictors: (Constant), family conflict Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (8.355) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.114), yielding $F = 73.155$. The model reveals that family conflict statistically and significantly at ($\text{Sig} = .000$) therefore it had a significant predictor at $F(3, 184) = 73.155$. The statistical results are given as; (family conflict; $\beta = .146$; $t = 3.118$; $p < 0.05$). The statistical result implies that family conflict had a statistically significant positive effect on Ekenedilichukwu.

Discussion of Findings

Hypothesis One: Succession Planning does not have Significant Positive Effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

F-value is the Mean Square Regression (6.708) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.142), yielding $F = 47.403$. From the results, the model in this table is statistically significant ($\text{Sig} = .000$). Therefore, succession planning had a significant positive effect on Ekenedilichukwu at $F(3, 184) = 47.403$. The result is in line with study of A research on succession planning and organizational survival was done by Osayande and Okolie (2016) using data from the National Business and Technical Examination Board in Benin City, Nigeria. The study's goal was to look at the impact of succession planning on organizational survival: Evidence from the Benin City-based National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB). The study's findings reveal that predictors have a considerable positive influence on response variables.

Hypothesis Two: Family Conflict does not have Significant Positive Effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

The model in this table shows that family conflict statistically and significantly at ($\text{Sig} = .008$) and had a significant positive effect on Ekenedilichukwu at $F(3, 184) = 4.035$. The statistical results is given as; (aesthetics $\beta = .019$; $t = .171$; $p > 0.05$). The statistical result implies that family conflict has statistically significant positive effect on Ekenedilichukwu. This is in line with study of Kemjika and Obikoya (2017) examined relationship between family conflict, values and school adjustment of secondary school adolescents in Rivers State Nigeria. The study investigated the relationship between family conflict, values and school adjustment of secondary

school adolescents in Rivers State. The study adopted correlational design targeted at establishing the relationship between family conflicts, values and school adjustment. The results of the study showed that there is a positive relationship between family conflict, values and school adjustment which are all statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Summary of Findings

- i. Succession planning had a significant positive effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.
- ii. Family conflict had a significant positive influence on performance of Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

Conclusion

Based on findings, we conclude that factor determinants of family-owned business failures had significant positive effect on Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company in Enugu, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The first factor is succession planning. Many people visit Ekenedirichukwu Transport due to their previous leadership functions, because they can check their car space, security and other security facilitates. Secondly family conflict is another factor. Here where there is misunderstanding between two family members. Based on the findings and conclusion reached, the study recommends that: Managers of Ekenedirichukwu Transport Company should consider succession planning and family conflict resolution as a powerful tool that affect family business failure. But they need to introduce strong policies towards succession planning and family conflict resolution within and outside family members.

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